

THE PROCESSING AND PROPERTIES OF
DAMAGE TOLERANT COMPOSITES BASED ON
K-POLYMER COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

K-polymer composite materials are based on a new family of thermoplastic polyimide matrix resins. High quality composites can be prepared under a wide variety of conditions by the vacuum bag autoclave or press molding of tacky drapable prepreg made using polyimide precursor solutions. In addition, the fully polymerized and volatiles free versions of this product offer the potential for automated tape or tow lay-down using a hot head. In tests run on graphite fiber reinforced composites, good strength retention out to temperatures as high as 232°C has been demonstrated. Such composites have also been shown to have excellent resistance to a wide variety of fluids of importance to the aerospace industry as well as outstanding damage tolerance. This unparalleled combination of processing capabilities, environmental resistance and mechanical properties make K-polymers prime matrix resin candidates for use with high performance fibers such as graphite and "Kevlar" 49, as well as glass, for primary aerospace structural applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

It has become increasingly apparent in recent years that for advanced composites to realize their full potential in the aerospace industry, new matrix resins would have to be developed. Such resins would need to have improved toughness and strain capability without significant penalties being paid in the areas of stiffness, strength, environmental resistance and upper end-use temperature. The net result would be composite structures which could be designed to higher strain levels taking full advantage of the new higher strain carbon fibers. In addition, such structure based on tough and resilient matrix resins would be far more damage resistant and damage tolerant than state-of-the-art 350°F epoxies (Reference 1).

Another goal of the aerospace industry has been the development of low cost thermoplastic processing techniques. If the tough, high strain matrix resins described above were also thermoplastic in nature, composite tapes and tows should lend themselves to rapid lay-down using automated tape laying or filament winding equipment employing a hot head. Flat sheet thermoforming would also represent one more example of a low cost fabrication technique which should be possible in composite parts based on thermoplastic matrix resins.

Du Pont has recently developed an approach based on K-polymer composite materials which holds great promise in meeting this demanding combination of requirements (References 2-4). K-polymers represent a new and unique family of thermoplastic polyimides which have been designed to have the processability, toughness and environmental resistance long sought after by the aerospace industry for load-bearing structural applications. Two members of this family have so far been identified for intensive study. K-I, with a glass transition temperature (Tg) of 200-210°C, has an upper end-use temperature, moisture considered, of about 177°C (350°F). K-II, on the other hand with a Tg of 220-280°C, has an estimated upper end-use temperature of 232°C (450°F).

The purpose of this paper is to highlight the major advances which have been made in developing a complete understanding of the processing characteristics and mechanical properties of composites based on K-polymer composite materials.

2. POLYIMIDE CHEMISTRY

2.1 General Background

In general, K-polymers are thermoplastic polyimides are produced in situ by the reaction of an aromatic diethyl ester diacid with an aromatic diamine dissolved in a suitable solvent such as N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP). The formation of the imide linkage with the evolution of volatile by-products (NMP, ethanol, and water) can be represented as follows:

Because of the essentially monomeric nature of the binder (polyimide precursor) solution, it is possible to prepare solutions having relatively low viscosities at relatively high solids contents. Such solutions are well suited for either hot melt or dip-coat/"B"-stage prepregging and are the basis for the prepregs whose processing and property characteristics are described in this paper.

2.2 TG-IR Studies

A convenient way of studying the course of cure is to analyze the composition of volatiles at different temperatures as the sample is heated to the point of complete cure. This has been done on the XP-1003 and XP-1004 polyimide precursor tapes which yield K-I and K-II polyimides, respectively, on "Magnamite" AS-4 graphite fibers. Samples of prepreg were heated in a thermogravimetric analyzer which was attached to a small (10 CC) infrared gas cell. Using nitrogen as the carrier gas, the off-gases were carried continuously into the cell where they were scanned every two minutes. The heat-up rate was 10°C/minute. From the data plotted in Figures 1 and 2 for the XP-1003 and XP-1004, respectively, several important points came to light:

- The onset of polymerization in both cases was about 135°C. It was at about this temperature that the chemically bound water and ethanol began to evolve.

- Absorbed atmospheric moisture appeared to be readily vaporized between room temperature and about 135°C.

- Most of the polymerization appeared to have been completed by the time temperatures in the 300-350°C range were reached.

- The monomers on the XP-1004 prepreg appeared to polymerize at somewhat lower temperatures than was the case for XP-1003 prepreg. The peak points for the evolution of water and ethanol were 10-20°C lower for XP-1004.

- At temperatures in excess of 400°C, significant quantities of CO₂ could be detected resulting from the thermal cracking of the aromatic crude² repeat units.

Additional refinements in the experimental technique are being made so that the course of evolution of higher boiling by-products such as NMP can be accurately monitored.

3. UNREINFORCED RESIN PROPERTIES

K-polymer powders can be isolated from the polyimide precursor solutions by curing and devolatilizing first at 180°C in a vacuum oven and then at 290°C in an oven under nitrogen. The pulverized polymer was then compression molded in a closed positive pressure mold at 371°C.

Table 1 summarizes the properties of unreinforced K-polymers and compares them with those of a typical aerospace epoxy (Reference 5). The T_{gs} have been measured by both thermal mechanical analysis as well as dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) and give about the same results, i.e., 210°C for K-I and 277°C for K-II. (See Figures 3 and 5 for the DMA curves.) Under water

FIGURE 1. TG-IR STUDY OF THE VOLATILES EVOLUTION FROM XP-1003 POLYIMIDE PRECURSOR TAPE

FIGURE 2. TG-IR STUDY OF THE VOLATILES EVOLUTION FROM XP-1004 POLYIMIDE PRECURSOR TAPE

Figure 3. Dynamic Mechanical Analysis of Dry K-I Polyimide.

TABLE 1

UNREINFORCED RESIN PROPERTIES

	<u>K-I</u>	<u>K-II</u>	<u>350°F Epoxy</u>
T _g , °C	210	277	190
T _m , °C	←————— None —————→		
Projected Upper End-Use Temperature, °C (°F)	177 (350)	232 (450)	135 (275)
Tensile Strength ¹ , psi	15,100	15,500	6600 ²
Tensile Modulus ¹ , psi	345,000	415,000	550,000 ²
Ultimate Strain ¹ , %	7	11	1 ²
G _{IC} , kJ/m ²	6.3	14	0.08 ³
Oxygen Index	50		
Char Yield, %	60		

¹Tested at 23°C

²Tested at 23°C

³Reference 5

Reference 6

saturated conditions (2 weeks submersed in water at 71°C), it is apparent from the DMA curves in Figures 4 and 6 for K-I and K-II, respectively, that significant loss in modulus and damping occurred at 177°C for K-I and 232°C for K-II. High levels of mechanical properties in laminates based on these two resins would not be expected above these temperatures. The weight gain for water saturated K-I was 0.9 percent and for K-II, 1.5 percent.

It should be noted that like the epoxy both K-I and K-II are amorphous polymers. Therefore, all problems associated with the development and control of the proper level of crystallinity throughout the life of the part are conveniently circumvented.

As indicated in Table 1, not only do K-polymers possess good levels of strength and stiffness, but they are also very tough. One indication of this is the ultimate strain-to-failure values of 7% and 11% for K-I and K-II, respectively. This compares with only 1% for the 350°F epoxy. Even more dramatic are the differences in fracture toughness (G_{IC}). Values of 6.3 kJ/m² and 14 kJ/m², which were measured on K-I and K-II, respectively, compared 0.08 kJ/m² for the epoxy. It was data of this kind that led us to believe from the outset that fiber reinforced composite structures based on K-polymers ought to possess levels of damage resistance and damage tolerance far superior to what is currently obtainable in composites based on 350°F aerospace epoxies.

4. LAMINATE FABRICATION

4.1 Prepreg Preparation

Except where indicated, all mechanical properties were measured on laminates cured in a vacuum bag under simulated autoclave molding conditions. The prepreg was prepared by impregnating collumated "MagnaMite" AS-4 graphite fibers with either the K-I or K-II types of polyimide precursor solutions. The prepreg so produced had volatiles contents in the 10-15% range. At the higher level of volatiles, the prepreg possesses good tack and drape under ambient conditions.

4.2 Lay-Up Procedures

In view of the fact that volatiles are evolved as a normal consequence of cure, provisions must be made so that this can be allowed to occur. In other words, the prepreg lay-up must not be sealed in. Three different lay-up techniques were employed: two-sided breathing, one-sided breathing with lay-up against the metal tool and one-sided breathing with lay-up against "Kapton" polyimide film.

The lay-up sequence for two-sided breathing was as follows:

Figure 4. Dynamic Mechanical Analysis of Water Saturated K-I Polyimide.

Figure 5. Dynamic Mechanical Analysis of Dry K-II Polyimide.

Figure 6. Dynamic Mechanical Analysis of Water Saturated K-II Polyimide.

Vacuum bag film or foil
Glass fabric
Caul plate
181 style E-glass fabric
112 style E-glass fabric
Porous PTFE coated glass fabric
Prepreg
Porous PTFE coated glass fabric
112 style E-glass fabric
181 style E-glass fabric
"Kapton" film
Mandrel (tool).

For laminations involving the XP-1003 polyimide precursor tape, the above lay-up sequence was exclusively employed with the exception that the prepreg was enclosed in an envelope of "Celgard" 4510 microporous polypropylene film to control resin flow. This procedure was not found to be necessary for the XP-1004 prepreg.

In the case of the XP-1004, laminations involving one-sided breathing were successfully carried out in which the prepreg was laid up directly against "Kapton" polyimide film or a stainless steel tool surface. Nonstainless steel surfaces invariably gave rise to laminates having severe microcracking on the surface. Lay-ups against both "Kapton" and stainless steel resulted in smooth defect-free surfaces. The top part of the lay-up, of course, was carried out as described above so that facile release of the volatile by-products could occur.

In the case of lay-ups directly against the stainless steel tool, a two-hour hold at the consolidation temperature prior to the application of pressure was found to be necessary when house vacuum (20-28 inches of Hg) was employed. If this were not done, surface microcracking would result. When full vacuum (29-30 inches of Hg) was used, such a hold was not to be found necessary.

4.3 General Steps Involved in Molding

In the molding of K-polymer composite materials, there are three basic steps. In the first step the prepreg lay-up is heated to the consolidation temperature under vacuum only. Some devolatilization with molecular weight buildup occurs. In order to control the bleeding of the binder when its viscosity is very low during the early stages of cure, it is necessary to carefully control the heat-up rate at about 2°C/minute. If heat-up is too rapid, excessive binder loss can occur. In the case of the K-I system, low vacuums (1-5 inches of mercury) are also required during the first phase of cure to prevent excessive resin bleeding.

In the second step, consolidation is carried out through the application of externally applied pressure. Consolidation must not be carried out too soon, otherwise excessive loss of binder can occur. The viscosity of the matrix at this point must be high enough to prevent excessive bleeding, but low enough to allow for adequate consolidation. Most of the porosity generated from trapped air and volatiles evolution up to this point in the cycle are eliminated.

In the third step, the laminate is heated to the final cure temperature. Residual volatiles are driven off with continuous reconsolidation. Finally, a high molecular weight, fully devolatilized matrix resin is produced in a laminate possessing low voids (<2%).

In general, the consolidation temperatures employed in this study were in the 135-200°C range. The minimum final molding temperature was 316°C for K-I based products and 343°C for K-II. Time at the final molding temperature was normally 3 hours using pressures of 100-200 psi. For a more detailed discussion of the details of processing, see Reference 4.

4.4 Laminate Characterization

All laminates made in this study were subjected to nondestructive evaluation using pulsed echo ultrasonic C-scanning equipment. This was found to be an excellent way of assessing overall laminate quality. In addition, the void content of each laminate was calculated based on its composition and component densities. As a further means of assessing laminate quality, selected cross-sections were mounted, polished and photographed. Few, if any, voids could be usually detected in laminates that had good C-scans and low calculated voids. Microscopic examination of fracture surfaces also indicated excellent adhesion between the K-polymer and the "Magnamite" AS-4 graphite fibers.

5. LAMINATE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

5.1 Flexural and Short Beam Shear Properties

A complete summary of the flexural strength, flexural modulus and short beam shear strength, both dry and water saturated, is given in Table 2. Note that after water saturation (2 weeks at 71°C) the T_g of K-I had been reduced from 208°C to 190°C as a result of the uptake of 0.33% water. The K-II laminates absorbed about 0.60% H₂O. This decreased the T_g from 264°C to 229°C. The epoxy had its initial T_g of 160°C decreased to 132°C as a result of a 0.93% weight gain. If the upper end-use temperature is defined as the temperature where, in the water saturated state, the strength properties are 50% of the room temperature properties measured on dry laminates, then the upper end-use temperature of laminates based on K-I and K-II are about 177°C (350°F) and 232°C (450°F), respectively. These results were compatible with the DMA data on unreinforced K-polymers described in Section 3. Note that even though the epoxy laminates started off with much higher strength values at room temperature, the values fell off sharply at elevated temperatures and, in fact, fell just below the levels for K-I at 177°C. Based on the above definition of upper end-use temperature, the value for the epoxy would be between 149°C and 177°C. However, the T_g of 132°C measured under water saturated conditions on an epoxy laminate would indicate that a more realistic projected upper end-use temperature would be about 135°C (275°F).

5.2 Compression After Impact

Quasi-isotropic laminates which were 4" x 6" x 0.2" were impacted in the center with a 0.625" diameter indenter up to an energy level of about 3000 inch pounds per inch of laminate thickness. In the through penetration test, a 0.5" diameter indenter was employed at an energy level of about 6000 inch

TABLE 2

MCHANICAL PROPERTY TESTING OF UNIDIRECTIONAL "MAGNAMITE" AS-4 LAMINATES
(NORMALIZED TO 60 VOLUME % FIBERS)

PROPERTY	"DRY"			"WET"		
	350°F	K-I	K-II	350°F	K-I	K-II
	EPOXY	POLYMER	POLYMER	EPOXY	POLYMER	POLYMER
FLEXURAL STRENGTH, PSI						
25°C	243,000	198,000	222,000	256,000	207,000	205,000
45°C	226,000	183,000		202,000	167,000	
121°C	213,000	175,000		173,000	161,000	
149°C	194,000	151,000	179,000	150,000	139,000	165,000
177°C	173,000	163,000	159,000	94,000	117,000	134,000
204°C			142,000			134,000
232°C			132,000			123,000
FLEXURAL MODULUS, PSI						
25°C	16x10 ⁶	17x10 ⁶	18x10 ⁶	18x10 ⁶	17x10 ⁶	17x10 ⁶
45°C	17x10 ⁶	17x10 ⁶	18x10 ⁶	18x10 ⁶	15x10 ⁶	17x10 ⁶
121°C	18x10 ⁶	17x10 ⁶	18x10 ⁶	18x10 ⁶	15x10 ⁶	17x10 ⁶
149°C	19x10 ⁶	17x10 ⁶	17x10 ⁶	18x10 ⁶	16x10 ⁶	16x10 ⁶
177°C	18x10 ⁶	17x10 ⁶	18x10 ⁶	17x10 ⁶	15x10 ⁶	16x10 ⁶
204°C			17x10 ⁶			16x10 ⁶
232°C			18x10 ⁶			18x10 ⁶
SHORT BEAM SHEAR STR., PSI						
25°C	16,500	16,000	13,600	15,000	13,800	12,500
45°C	15,000	13,000		10,900	10,600	
121°C	11,700	11,600		8,700	9,900	
149°C	11,400	10,400	10,300	8,300	8,600	9,900
177°C	9,400	7,900	9,200	5,800	7,600	9,400
204°C			9,800			8,700
232°C			8,200			6,800
16, °C	168	208	264	132	190	229
Δ WT. GAIN				0.93	0.33	0.60

°EXPOSED TO H₂O FOR 2 WEEKS AT 71°C

pounds/inch. An accelerometer in the indenter allowed for a force-displacement curve to be obtained which made it possible to calculate how much energy was actually required to achieve through penetration. The tests were run on both K-I and K-II based laminates reinforced with "MagnaMite" AS-4/graphite fibers at a concentration of about 60 volume %.

From the data plotted in Figures 7 and 8, it can be seen that both the K-I and K-II based laminates possessed excellent damage resistance and damage tolerance. In Figure 7 in which the percent compressive strain is plotted vs impact energy, the strain values for the K-polymer laminates were found to fall off only very gradually with increasing impact energy. In other words, the laminates were very damage resistant. Even when the impact energy was high enough (about 4000 inch lb/in) to cause actual through penetration, the damage was sufficiently localized so that residual compressive strain levels in the 0.5-0.7% range were still retained. This indicated that the laminates were very damage tolerant. A similar story unfolds in Figure 8 where compressive stress values are plotted against impact energy. At the point of through penetration, both types of K-polymer laminates had compressive strength values of about 30,000 psi.

By comparison, the performance of a typical 350°F epoxy laminate ("Thorne1" 300/Narmco 5208) was very poor (Reference 1). According to the data plotted in Figures 7 and 8, the epoxy laminates were neither damage resistant nor damage tolerant. The reason, of course, is the extreme brittleness of the epoxy matrix. The very low unreinforced ultimate strain-to-failure and fracture toughness values of the unreinforced resin have resulted in excessive microcracking and delamination. Thus, the area of damage extended far beyond the point of impact with the resultant weakening of the structure.

5.3 Uniaxial Compressive Properties

Based on the ASTM D-695 test, unidirectional K-I/"MagnaMite" AS-4 graphite fiber laminates have been shown to have compressive strengths as high as 175,000 psi (dry/23°C) and 132,000 psi (wet/82°C). Higher values are anticipated following the completion of improved compressive test procedures. Results involving K-II laminates will be reported on at a later time.

5.4 ±45° Tensile Testing

Further evidence for the great strength and ductility of K-polymers has come from the tensile testing of +45° laminates. A K-I/"MagnaMite" AS-4 laminate containing 54 volume % fibers had a tensile strength of 44,000 psi at room temperature. This compared with a value of only 25,000 psi for a 350°F epoxy laminate containing 60 volume % fibers. K-II laminates are also expected to perform well in this test.

5.5 Creep Testing

In preliminary studies involving tensile creep in +45° laminates, the K-I/"MagnaMite" AS-4 system exhibited the same low level of creep as that found for 350°F epoxy laminates. The tests were run at room temperature with a tensile load amounting to 5000 psi. Tests involving K-II are forthcoming.

Figure 7.

EFFECT OF IMPACT ENERGY ON THE COMPRESSIVE STRAIN OF QUASI-ISOTROPIC LAMINATES

Figure 8.

EFFECT OF IMPACT ENERGY ON THE COMPRESSIVE STRESS OF QUASI-ISOTROPIC LAMINATES

It is, therefore, apparent that the thermoplastic K-polymer matrix did not in any way cause more creep than that found in the highly crosslinked 350°F epoxy.

5.6 Fatigue Testing

In 3-point flexural fatigue tests run on unidirectional K-I/"MagnaMite" AS-4 laminates at 60% of the ultimate flexural stress, the endurance limit was found to be 850,000 cycles. Although this was not quite as good as that found for the 350°F epoxy laminate ($>10^7$ cycles to failure), it is anticipated that the fatigue endurance of off-axis laminates can be superior in the K-polymer laminates. Under such conditions, the toughness of the K-polymer matrix should have much greater chance to manifest itself.

5.7 Fabric Laminates

For a summary of the mechanical properties of type A-193P "MagnaMite" AS-4 0/90 graphite fabric (plain weave) laminates, see Table 3. It can be seen that very high flexural and short beam shear strength values (121,000 psi and 12,300 psi, respectively) were measured at room temperature for the K-I system. Equally as good results are anticipated for the K-II matrix (to be reported on at a later time).

6. ENVIRONMENTAL TESTING OF LAMINATES

Unidirectional K-I and K-II laminates were exposed to a wide variety of fluids of interest to the aerospace industry for periods of 1 to 14 days. The results are summarized in Table 4. In all cases, the percent weight gains were low. For laminates exposed at room temperature to Monsanto's low density aviation hydraulic test fluid, methyl ethyl ketone, ethylene glycol deicing fluid, JP-4 jet fuel and methylene chloride paint stripper, no solvent induced stress cracks were noted even though the laminates were under a flexural strain of about 0.6%. In every instance there was at least a 91% retention of short beam shear strength measured at room temperature. Thus the organic fluids did not significantly plasticize nor weaken the K-polymer matrix. In addition, there was no indication that the fluids adversely affected the fiber/matrix adhesion. These results indicate the high degree of resistance to organic fluids which can be achieved in K-polymer laminates in spite of the amorphous nature of the resins.

In alkaline cleaner (PACE B-82, diluted with 2 parts water to 1 part B-82), there was a small amount of surface attack. This attack was somewhat less in the K-II laminate than in the K-I. In both cases, the attack was only on the surface. The excellent retention of short beam shear strength for both systems indicated that there was no overall effect on the matrix.

7. LAMINATES FROM "KEVLAR" ARAMID FIBER

The inherent toughness and noncatastrophic failure mode of "Kevlar" aramid fiber make it of special interest in advanced structural composites. K-polymer composites reinforced with "Kevlar" 49 promise uniquely high levels of toughness, and work is underway to develop processing conditions compatible with "Kevlar." This work will be reported at a later date.

TABLE 3

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF K-I/O-90 "MAGNAMITE" AS-4
A-193P GRAPHITE FABRIC LAMINATES

<u>Properties</u>	<u>Value</u>
Flexural Strength, psi	
23°C	121,000
93°C	104,000
Flexural Modulus, psi	
23°C	9.4×10^4
93°C	9.3×10^4
Short Beam Shear Strength, psi	
23°C	12,300
93°C	10,700
Volume % Fibers	59
Tg, °C	201

TABLE 4

ENVIRONMENTAL TESTING OF UNIDIRECTIONAL "MAGNAMITE" AS-4 LAMINATES
(THICKNESS = 90-100 MILS)

FLUID	EXPOSURE TEMP., °C	EXPOSURE TIME, HOURS	K-I POLYMER		K-II POLYMER	
			% WT GAIN	SHORT BEAM SHEAR STR. x10 ⁻³ PSI	% WT GAIN	SHORT BEAM SHEAR STR. ⁵ x10 ⁻³ PSI
NONE - CONTROL				16.0		13.6
H ₂ O	71	336	0.28	13.8	0.60	13.1
ALKALINE CLEANER ¹	71	336	0.10	14.1	0.60	13.0
HYDRAULIC FLUID ²	25 ⁴	336	0.036	15.4	0	13.0
	71	336	0.036	15.4	0.02	12.7
MEK	25 ⁴	336	0.12	14.9	0.10	13.9
JP-4	25 ⁴	336	0.012	14.6	0	13.1
DEICING ³	23 ⁴	336	0.003	15.6	0.04	14.0
CH ₂ CL ₂	25 ⁴	24	0.24	15.7	0.49	13.9

¹ PALLE B-82 DILUTED WITH 2 PARTS H₂O TO 1 PART B-82.

² MONSANTO LOW DENSITY AVIATION HYDRAULIC TEST FLUID.

³ DOW AIRCRAFT DEICING FLUID 146AR.

⁴ EXPOSED UNDER STRESS - NO STRESS-CRACKING DETECTED.

⁵ TESTED AT 25°C.

Table 5

Simulated vs Actual Autoclave Molding of
XP-1004 Polyimide Precursor Tape

<u>Properties</u>	<u>Simulated Autoclave Molding</u>	<u>Autoclave Molding</u>
Flexural Strength, psi	90,700	95,200
Flexural Modulus, psi	3.7×10^6	3.7×10^6
Flexural Strain, %	3.2	3.5
Volume % Fibers	65	62

8. SIMULATED VS ACTUAL AUTOCLAVE OF XP-1004 POLYIMIDE PRECURSOR TAPE

Although most of the studies carried out in this program involved simulated autoclave molding in a press, some work was done in a nitrogen pressured autoclave. Preliminary studies indicate that under a given set of conditions, essentially the same results can be obtained by both processes. This is illustrated in Table 5. In both cases lay-up was against "Kapton" with consolidation temperatures in the 170-180°C range employing house vacuum (22-28 inches of Hg). The autoclave molded part employed 100 psi pressure compared with 200 psi for the simulated autoclave run in a press. Final molding conditions were 3 hours at 343°C in both cases. Note that the room temperature flexural properties of the autoclave molded 8-ply 3" x 5" quasi-isotropic XP-1004 laminate were at least as good as the same type of panel made in the press.

9. AUTOMATED THERMOPLASTIC TAPE LAYDOWN

K-polymers offer great versatility in part fabrication. As indicated above, tacky drapable prepregs can be prepared which can either be handled manually or laid down on today's automated laydown equipment designed for epoxies. A vacuum bag/autoclave cure, of course, must be carried out to remove solvent and affect condensation polymerization. In addition, fiber reinforced tapes and tows are under development where the K-polymer matrix is of high molecular weight and solvent free. Preliminary results from the laydown of a K-I/"Magnamite" AS-4 thermoplastic tape have been promising. Values of 168,000 psi and 14,900 psi have been found for the flexural and short beam shear strengths, respectively, at room temperature. These values are about 85% of the values obtained by vacuum bag/simulated autoclave molding. Additional studies in this important new area of thermoplastic tape laydown are in progress and will be reported on at a later time. In addition, other thermoplastic processing techniques such as flat sheet thermoforming and pultrusion should also be feasible with K-polymer composite materials.

10. SUMMARY

- A new family of amorphous thermoplastic polyimides, designated K-polymers, has been developed for use as matrix resins in advanced structural aerospace composites.

- Graphite fiber reinforced laminates based on K-polymers have been shown to have outstanding impact damage resistance and damage tolerance as well as excellent environmental resistance.

- Two versions of K-polymer composite materials were developed. K-I composites were shown to have an upper end-use temperature potentially as high as 177°C (350°F). K-II composites were shown to have good strength retention out to 232°C (450°F).

- Preliminary studies indicate that K-polymer composite materials have excellent autoclave moldability.

- K-polymer composite materials are being developed in two basic product forms. The first is a tacky, drapable prepreg which can be laid up and vacuum bag/autoclave molded using today's technology. The second is a dry

high molecular weight thermoplastic tape or tow product capable of automated laydown using a hot head.

11. REFERENCES

1. B.A. Bayers, NASA Contractor Report 159290, August, 1980.
2. H.H. Gibbs, "K-Polymer: A New Experimental Matrix Resin for Advanced Structural Aerospace Composites," pgs. 1873-1884, 29th Annual SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition, Reno, Nevada, April 3-5, 1984.
3. H.H. Gibbs, "K-Polymer Composite Materials - A New Approach to Damage Tolerant Aerospace Structures," SAE Aerospace Congress, Long Beach, California, October 15-18, 1984.
4. H.H. Gibbs, "Processing Studies on K-Polymer Composite Materials Part I - Prepregs Based on K-II Polyimide," 30th Annual SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition, Anaheim, California, March 19-21, 1985.
5. J.M. Augl, "Moisture Effects With Mechanical Properties of Hercules' 3501-6 Epoxy Resin," Naval Surface Weapons Center Report TR 79-41, March, 1979.
6. W.D. Bascom, J.C. Bitner and R.L. Cottingham, "The Fracture Energy of High Performance Polymers," Organic Coatings and Plastics Chemistry, Vol. 38, 1978, pgs. 477-484.

12. BIOGRAPHY

Dr. Hugh H. Gibbs is a Senior Research Associate with the Polymer Products Department of Du Pont where he has been employed since 1956. He received his BSC (1952) and MSC (1953) from Queen's University (Canada) and PhD (1956) in Organic Chemistry from the University of Illinois. During the past 15 years he has been responsible for the development of melt-fusible polyimides for use in high performance composites. More recently this has expanded to include thermoplastic composites in general.

Note: This development has been strictly at the research level. No decision has been made as to the commercialization of any of the systems described in this paper.

